

Quantum Theory from Problems to Advances – QTPA

June 9-12, 2014. Arrival June 8, departure June 13

Program of the Conference

Arranged by ICMM - International Centre for Mathematical Modeling in Physics,
Engineering and Cognitive Sciences; Linnaeus University, Sweden

See <http://lnu.se/qtpa>

Organization committee, QTAP:

- *H. De Raedt (Univ. of Groningen, the Netherlands)*
- *Yu. Hasegawa (Atom Institute, Austrian Academy of Science, Austria)*
- *A. Khrennikov (Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden)*
- *A. Migdall (NIST, USA)*
- *A. Plotnitsky (Purdue University, USA)*
- *S. Polyakov (NIST, USA)*

Local organizing committee:

Andrei Khrennikov, Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden.

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Special Sessions:

- **Testing boundaries of Quantum theory: experiment and its interpretation** (Organizers: Alan Migdall and Sergey Polyakov)
- **Relativity meets Quantum Theory**
(Organizer: Giacomo Mauro D'Ariano)
- **Quantum Foundations meet General Relativity**
(Organizers: Markus Aspelmeyer and Caslav Brukner)
- **Philosophical significance of quantum reconstruction theorems**
(Organizers: Guido Bacciagaluppi and Philip Goyal)

Main conference auditorium: Wicksell, main building H, Linnaeus University, Växjö

8.30-9.15	Registration: outside the main conference room Wicksell	
Wicksell		
9.00-9.15	Opening Ceremony: S. Hwang, rector of Linnaeus University	
Chairman: Theo Nieuwenhuizen		
9.20-9.50	A. Plotnitsky (Purdue University, USA)	“The Measure of the Universe:” Revisiting Reality and Realism in Quantum Theory
9.50-10.20	V. Scarani (National University of Singapore, Singapore)	Randomness from quantum systems: a guided tour
10.20-10.50	A. Hosoya (Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan)	Weak Value in Young's Double Slit Experiment
10.50-11.20	Coffee break	
SPECIAL SESSION: Testing boundaries of Quantum Theory		
Wicksell	Chairman: Sergey Polyakov	
11.20-11.50	S. Ritter (Max-Planck-Institut für Quantenoptik, Germany)	Nondestructive Detection of an Optical Photon
11.55-12.25	A. Migdall (NIST & Univ. Maryland)	Photon-number-resolved detection: Pushing the limits in nonorthogonal state discrimination
12.30-13.00	Th. Monz (University of Innsbruck, Austria)	Finding systematic errors in tomographic data: Characterising ion-trap quantum computers
13.10-14.30	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Wicksell	SPECIAL SESSION: Testing boundaries of Quantum Theory	
Chairman: Alan Migdall		
14.30-15.00	S. Polyakov (NIST, USA)	Novel metrological methods for quantum sources and detectors
15.05-15.35	Y. Zhang (University of Waterloo, Canada)	Analysis of tests of local realism
15.40 -16.10	Z. Levine (National Institute of Standards and Technology, USA)	Quantifying photon number uncertainty between individual photons and shot noise
16.10-16.30	Coffee Break	

PARALLELL SESSIONS		Session 1: K1040 Session 2:K1043 Session 3: K1046
Session 1: K1040	Chairman: Stephan Ritter	
16.30-16.50	A. de Barros (San Francisco State University, USA)	Measuring Contextuality in Quantum Systems
16.55-17.15	E. Loubenets (Moscow State Institute of Electronics and Mathematics, Russia)	Context-independent quasi hidden variables (qHV) modelling of all joint von Neumann measurements for an arbitrary Hilbert space
17.20 -17.40	M. Pusey (Perimeter Institute, Canada)	Beyond local causality
17.45-18.05	H. Heydari (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Geometry and structure of quantum phase space
18.05-18.15	Short break	
K1040	Chairman: Elena Loubents	
18.15-18.35	S. Glancy (National Institute of Standards and Technology, USA)	Bell Inequalities for Time-tagged Detections
18.40-19.00	G. Oas (Stanford University, USA)	Proposed principles behind quantum mechanics examined through negative probability
Session 2: K1043	Chairman: Gerard Milburn	
16.30-16.50	J. Franson (University of Maryland Baltimore County, USA)	Quantum Mechanics in Curved Spacetime: A Quantum-Mechanical Correction to the Speed of Light
16.55-17.15	L. Gyongyosi (Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Hungary)	Information Processing Structure of Quantum Gravity
17.20-17.40	Y. Shikano (Institute for Molecular Science, Japan)	Aharonov-Bohm Effect with Quantum Tunneling
17.45-18.05	R. Kostecki (Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics, Canada)	Quantum information geometric foundations
18.05-18.15	Short break	
K1043	Chairman Laszlo Gyongyosi	
18.15-18.35	H. Westman (CSIC, Spain)	Qubits in curved spacetimes
18.40-19.00	D. Galehouse (University of Akron, USA)	Quantum mechanics as geometry: Conflict, Mechanism, Interpretation, and Implication
Session 3: K1046	Chairman: Arkady Plotnitsky	
16.30-16.50	L. Marchildon (Universite du Quebec, Canada)	Why I am not a QBist
16.55-17.15	B. Khots (Compressor Controls Corporation, USA)	Einstein photoelectric effect theory and Lamb – Scully and Hanbury-Brown Twiss experiments from Observer’s Mathematics point of view

17.20 -17.40	P. Hoehn (Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics, USA)	A novel approach to characterising quantum theory based on limited information and complementarity
17.45-18.05	H. Yau (FDNL Research)	Quantum Properties of a Field with Time as a Dynamical Variable
18.05-18.15	Short break	

19.00 - Welcome buffe at restaurant “Kristina”, building H

Myrdal	Chairman: Antonio Acin	
9.00-9.30	S. Ramelow (University of Vienna, Austria)	On Closing Loopholes in Bell Experiments
9.30-10.00	A. Zeilinger (Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria)	Quantum Imaging with Undetected Photons: The role of Information
10.05-10.35	G. Björk (Royal Inst. of Technology, Sweden)	Synthetic observables and the eigenvalue problem
10.35-11.00	Coffee Break	
	Parallel Sessions of invited talks: 11.00-12.30 Session 1: Myrdal Session 2: Weber	
Session 1: Myrdal	Chairman: Sven Ramelow	
11.00-11.30	A. Khrennikov (Linnaeus University, Sweden)	Classical probabilistic model for the CHSH inequality: is there a difference between classical and quantum randomness?
11.30-12.00	H. De Raedt (University of Groningen, The Netherlands)	From logical inference to quantum theory
12.00-12.30	K. Michielsen (Juelich Supercomputing Centre, Germany)	Event-by-event simulation of photon bunching experiments
12.30-13.00	J. Kofler (Max Planck Institute of Quantum Optics (MPQ), Germany)	Necessary adaptation of the CH/Eberhard inequality bound for a loophole-free Bell test
Session 2: Weber	Chairman : Marcus Appleby	
11.00-11.30	I. Bengtsson (Stockholms Universitet, Sweden)	Why are SICS interesting?
11.30-12.00	J. M. Dahlström (Max Planck Institute for the Physics of Complex Systems, Germany)	Photoionization probed on the attosecond time scale
12.00-12.30	T. Nieuwenhuizen (University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands)	The hydrogen ground state in stochastic electrodynamics
12.30-13.00	G. Jaeger (Boston University, USA)	Macroscopicity and Quantum Measurement
13.00-14.30	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Myrdal	Chairman: Gunnar Björk	
14.30-15.00	A. Acin (ICFO-The Institute of Photonic Sciences, Spain)	Implications of computer science principles for quantum physics
15.00-15.30	M. Ozawa (Nagoya University, Japan)	Tight error-disturbance relation for qubit measurements in mixed states
15.30-16.00	Yu. Hasegawa (Vienna University of Technology, Austria)	Quantum Cheshire-Cat and weak values investigated with neutron's matter-wave

16.00-16.15	Coffee Break	
SPECIAL SESSION: Relativity meets Quantum Theory		
Myrdal	Chairman: T. Nieuwenhuizen	
16.15-16.45	G. Amelino Camelia (Sapienza University of Rome, Italy)	Planck-scale quantum mechanics with deformed relativistic symmetries
16.45--17.15	G. M. D'Ariano (Università degli Studi di Pavia, Italy)	Recent progresses in the Quantum Cellular Automaton extension of Quantum Field Theory
17.15-17.45	P. Perinotti (Università di Pavia, Italy)	Quantum cellular automata and the electromagnetic field
17.45-18.15	A. Plotnitsky (Purdue University, USA)	A Matter of Principle: The Principles of Quantum Theory, Relativity, Dirac's Equation, and Quantum Information

Wednesday, 11th of June 2014

9.00-12.50	Invited talks in two parallel sessions	Session1: Wicksell Session2:K1043
Session1: Wicksell	Chairman: Ehtibar Dzhafarov	
9.00-9.30	R. Gill (Leiden University, The Netherlands)	Learning from experience: lessons from engagement with quantum crackpots
9.30-10.00	J.-Å. Larsson (Linköpings Universitet, Sweden)	Bell violation with entangled photons, free of the coincidence-time loophole
10.00-10.30	M. Kupczynski (Quebec University (UQO), Canada)	Probabilistic models, experimental protocols and contextuality of quantum theory
10.30-10.50	Coffee Break	
Wicksell	Chairman: Richard Gill	
10.50-11.20	E. Dzhafarov (Purdue University, USA)	The nature and measures of probabilistic contextuality
11.20-11.50	S. Abramsky (University of Oxford, UK)	Contextual Semantics
11.50-12.20	B. Coecke (Oxford University, UK)	Picturing Quantum Processes
12.20-12.50	E. Haven (University of Leicester, UK)	How potential functions can aid us in modelling basic finance concepts
Session2: K1043	Chairman: Harald Atmanspacher	
9.00-9.30	O. Manko (Lebedev Physical Institute, Russia)	Generalized qubit portrait of the qutrit-state density matrix
9.30-10.00	B. C. Hiesmayr (University of Vienna, Austria)	Testing Foundations of Quantum Mechanics in High Energy Physics
10.00-10.30	C. O. Curceanu (LNF-INFN, Italy)	From the chrono-synclastic infundibulum to the collapse of the wave function
10.30-10.50	Coffee Break	
K1043	Chairman: Olga Manko	
10.50-11.20	F. De Martini (Accademia dei Lincei, Italy)	Demonstration of the Spin-Statistics theorem by Conformal Quantum Geometroynamics
11.20-11.50	H. Atmanspacher (ETH Zurich, Switzerland)	Non-commuting observables in classical dynamical systems
11.50-12.20	B. Nilsson (Linnaeus University, Sweden)	Source characterization in optical fibres with quantum tomography
12.20-12.50	N. Watanabe (Tokyo University of Science, Japan)	On entropy of quantum compound systems

12.55-14.30	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Wicksell	SPECIAL SESSION: Quantum Foundations meet General Relativity	
Chairman: James Franson		
14.30-14.50	M. Aspelmeyer and C. Brukner	Introduction
14.50-15.20	D. Greenberger	The necessity of treating mass and proper time as dynamical variables, and some consequences
15.20-15.50	G. Milburn (The University of Queensland, Australia)	Gravitational decoherence
15.50-16.10	Coffee break	
Wicksell	SPECIAL SESSION: Quantum Foundations meet General Relativity	
Chairman: Markus Aspelmeyer		
16.10-16.40	Ni. Kiesel (University of Vienna, Austria)	Towards quantum experiments with levitated nanoparticles
16.40-17.10	M. Zych (IQOQI, Austria)	Quantum Extension of the Einstein Equivalence Principle
17.10-17.40	C. Gooding (University of British Columbia, Canada)	Self-gravitating Interferometry and Intrinsic Decoherence

19.00-22.00 Conference dinner at restaurant “Villa Vik”

Address: Toftastrand Hotell & Konditori / Villa Viks matsalar, Lenhovdavagen 72, SE-352 49 Vaxjo, Sweden; Web-page: http://www.villavik.se/restaurant_eng.shtml

Transfer: **Conference Bus goes at**

18.20 University -> **18.30** Elite Stadshotellet -> **18.40** Elite Park Hotel Konserthuset -> **19.00** Villa Vik

Conference Bus at 22.00 goes

Villa Vik -> Elite Park Hotel Konserthuset -> Elite Stadshotellet -> University

Parallel Sessions of contributed talks: 9.30-15.50 Session 1:K1211 Session 2: Weber Special session 3:Philosophical significance of quantum reconstruction theorems at Wicksell		
Session 1: K1211	Chairman: Jan-Åke Larsson	
9.30-9.50	B. Marques (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Experimental Implementation Hardy-Like Proof of Quantum Contextuality
9.55-10.15	T. Kauten (University of Innsbruck, Austria)	Testing the Foundations of Quantum Mechanics with Multipath Interferometers and Single Photons
10.20-10.40	J. Fors (Linköping University, Sweden)	Finding the limits of the coincidence-time loophole for the Braunstein-Caves inequality
10.45-11.05	W. Rosenfeld (Ludwig-Maximilians-University, Germany)	Heralded entanglement of single neutral atoms for a loophole-free test of Bell's inequality
11.05-11.30	Coffee Break	
K1211	Chairman: Beatrix C. Hiesmayr	
11.30-11.50	A. Asadian (Atominstitut, Austria)	Probing macroscopic realism via Ramsey correlation measurements
11.55-12.15	Ä. Baumeler (Università della Svizzera italiana, Switzerland)	Classical multi-party signaling can maximally violate predefined causal order
12.20-12.50	J. Leon (Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas, Spain)	Local quanta, unitary inequivalence, and vacuum entanglement
13.00-14.15	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
K1211	Chairman: Olga Manko	
14.15-14.35	K. Redeker (Ludwig-Maximilians Universität München, Germany)	Fast and efficient detection of atomic states for a loophole free test of Bell's inequality
14.40-15.00	A. Bolotin (Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel)	Computational solution to quantum foundational problems
15.05-15.25	I. Barukcic (University of Hamburg, Germany)	Anti Newton - Refutation Of The Constancy Of Newton's Gravitational Constant G
15.30-15.50	R. Roknizadeh (University of Isfahan, Iran)	Three Types of Generalized Coherent States For Nonlinear Harmonic Oscillator

Session 2: Weber	Chairman: Francesco De Martini	
9.30-9.50	O. Andersson (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Mandelstam-Tamm quantum speed limits for driven systems in mixed states
9.55-10.15	A. Akhmeteli (LTASolid Inc., USA)	No Drama Quantum Electrodynamics?
10.20-10.40	S. Rankovic (ETH Zurich, Switzerland)	The alternate ticks time game
10.45-11.05	A. S. Sanz (Instituto de Física Fundamental (IFF-CSIC), Spain)	Investigating hidden aspects of quantum theory by means of its hydrodynamic representation
11.05-11.30	Coffee break	
Weber	Chairman: Acacio De Barros	
11.30-11.50	M. Appleby (University of Sydney, Australia)	Mind and Matter
11.55-12.15	P. Khrennikova (Leicester University, UK)	Order effect and U.S. voters' preferences: quantum framework representation of the observables
12.20-12.50	A. Tavakoli (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Quantum Strategies in Bridge Game
13.00-14.15	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Weber	Chairman: Marcus Appleby	
14.15-14.35	C. Pombo (The Netherlands)	Differentiation with stratification: a guiding principle of theoretical physics, in the tradition of the Lullian art
14.40-15.00	E. Rosinger (University of Pretoria, South Africa)	A disconnect: limitations of the axiomatic method in physics
15.05-15.25	S. Dunder-Coecke (UK)	A quest for new quantum words: Reasons
15.30-15.50	H. K. Tank (Indian Space Research Organization, India)	Complete Explanation for the Double Slit Particle-Interference Experiments
Session 3 Wicksell	SPECIAL SESSION: Philosophical significance of quantum reconstruction theorems	
9.20-9.30	G. Bacciagaluppi and P. Goyal	Wellcome to the session
Chairman: Guido Bacciagaluppi		
9.30-10.00	M. D'Ariano (Università degli Studi di Pavia, Italy)	Informational Principles for Quantum Theory, the Operational Framework, and the Scientific Method
10.00-10.30	C. Brukner (University of Vienna, Austria)	Quantum theory: First reconstruction and then interpretation
10.30-11.00	M. Mueller (Heidelberg University, Germany)	Quantum theory and spacetime: progress from principles
11.05-11.30	Coffee Break	

Wicksell		Chairman: Markus Mueller
11.30-12.00	P. Goyal (University at Albany (SUNY), USA)	Reconstruction of Feynman's Formulation of Quantum Theory, and its Implications
12.00-12.30	G. Bacciagaluppi (University of Aberdeen, UK)	Top-down and bottom-up approaches to quantum mechanics
12.30-13.00	A. Stairs (University of Maryland, USA)	Quantum Reconstruction and Quantum Logic
13.00-14.15	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Wicksell		Chairman: Philip Goyal
14.15-14.45	A. Grinbaum (CEA-Saclay, France)	Bohr's "common language" as a basis for reconstructing quantum theory
14.45-15.15	M. Dickson (University of South Carolina, USA)	Reinvention Theorems
15.15-15.45	General discussion	
15.50	<i>Conference closing ceremony at Wicksell</i>	

POSTER SESSION

A. Avanesov (Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology, Russia)	Wave function of classical system and analogue of entanglement
I. Barukcic (University of Hamburg, Germany)	Anti Heisenberg - Refutation of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle II
L. Gyongyosi (Budapest Univ. of Tech., Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Hungary)	Multiuser Quadrature Allocation for Continuous-Variable Quantum Key Distribution
L. Gyongyosi (Budapest Univ. of Tech., Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Hungary)	Quantum Imaging of High-Dimensional Hilbert Spaces with Radon Transform
Y. Han and C. Li (University of Science and Technology of China, China)	Quantum simulation of Landau-Zener model supporting the Kibble-Zurek mechanism
Y. Shikano (Institute for Molecular Science, Japan)	Visualization of Polarized State by Weak Measurement
L. Markovich (Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology State University, Russia)	Separability, entanglement and Minkowski type inequality of the qudit X-state with $j=3/2$

Information

Location:

- The conference will take place at Linnaeus University, Växjö.
- Main conference room: Wicksell, in building H.

Transportation:

From Resecentrum (located close to the train station) to the Universitetet. To come to the first lecture of morning sessions, the bus number 3 at 8.30 from Train station seems the most convenient.

By fair weather, it is also possible to walk to the university along the lakes. It takes between 40 and 50 minutes.